

Effectiveness of Universal Design of Learning on Academic Achievement of the Students in Inclusive Classroom

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INTRODUCTION

A disability is a condition or function that is significantly impaired compared to the typical standard of an individual or group. The term encompasses various aspects of individual functioning, including physical, sensory, cognitive, and intellectual impairments, as well as mental illnesses and chronic diseases. Children who require specialized support and accommodations beyond those needed by their peers are referred to as children with special needs. Every classroom consists of students with diverse abilities, making it essential to recognize and embrace this diversity. At some point during our school or college years, each of us has encountered a need for special support.

In this study the research studied the effectiveness of UDL in an inclusive classroom. The objectives of the study were to apply the Universal Design of Learning to teach the students in Inclusive classroom at elementary level and to identify the effect of Universal Design of Learning on the students' Learning. Experimental method was used in the study. Total 40 students from class 4th & 5th from the govt. school of Delhi was the sample of the study. t test was used for analysis the data. Researcher has found that there was a significance difference between the mean academic achievement scores of pre-test and post-test after the use of universal design of learning in Inclusive Classroom.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The statement of the problem is "Effectiveness of Universal design of Learning on Academic achievement in Inclusive Classroom."

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Preety & Rekha(2024) said that Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is a framework that aims to promote inclusive education by providing multiple means of representation, expression and engagement for all learners. This paper explores the principles of UDL and its potential impact on designing learning experiences for all learners. The paper begins with an overview of the UDL principles, including its three main guidelines: providing multiple means of representation, multiple means of expression and multiple means of engagement. The paper also explores the practices of UDL, such as perceptible, equitable use, flexibility, personal assistants, simple, intuitive use, tolerance and low efforts. Additionally, the challenges of implementing UDL in practice are discussed, such as the need for professional development, access to resources and overcoming resistance to change.

Sharma, B.U. (2024) examined the impact of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) on student engagement and achievement within inclusive education settings. Inclusive education aims to create environments where all students, regardless of their backgrounds, abilities, or learning styles, can thrive. UDL is a proactive framework designed to remove learning barriers through its core principles of multiple means of engagement, representation, and action and expression. A systematic search of scholarly databases including ERIC, Education Research Complete, and

PsycINFO was conducted, employing keywords such as "Universal Design for Learning," "inclusive education," and "student engagement." The synthesis of research indicates that UDL significantly enhances student engagement by providing diverse ways for students to connect with learning material and promotes a sense of ownership and self-regulation. Additionally, UDL correlates with improved academic achievement by offering multiple pathways for demonstrating knowledge, particularly benefiting students with learning disabilities. While UDL shows promise in transforming inclusive classrooms, the research highlights the importance of ongoing professional development and fidelity of implementation to maximize its benefits.

Rao et.al, (2021), who endorse this viewpoint, claim that digital portfolios can give learners an authentic opportunity to self-reflect on progress, highlight accomplishments and share work with their peers. Digital tools can assist students create ideas progressively and share them with their peers.

Hall, Meyer, and Rose (2017) highlighted that students are more likely to be motivated and actively participate when they can access material in ways that resonate with them. For example, some students might engage better with visual aids, while others might prefer hands-on activities or auditory inputs. By incorporating various methods of presenting information, UDL ensures that students are not only passive recipients of knowledge but active participants in their learning process.

Meyer, Rose, and Gordon (2014) showed that students in UDL-implemented classrooms often outperform their peers in traditional classrooms. This performance boost is attributed to the customized and flexible learning environment that UDL promotes. Students are not constrained by a single method of instruction, which can be particularly beneficial for those who do not thrive under conventional teaching methods.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Following were the major objectives of the study:

1. To apply the Universal Design of Learning to teach the students in Inclusive classroom.
2. To identify the effect of Universal Design of Learning on the students' Learning.

HYPOTHESIS

To attain these objectives, the null hypothesis was formulated:

1. There is no significance difference between the mean score of academic achievement of the pre-test and post-test after the treatment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the present research was to check the effectiveness of Universal Design of Learning on the Academic Achievement of the student in Inclusive Classroom. The research was an experimental study. Universal Design of learning was independent variable and Academic Achievement of the student was dependent variable. For experimentation, Students from 4th and 5th class was selected and the one-group pretest-post test design was used.

POPULATION

The population consisted on the students who were studying in 4th and 5th class in Government Primary Schools situated in Delhi.

SAMPLE

One of the Government Primary School was randomly selected as a sample school. Then 40 students from 4th and 5th class were randomly selected.

INSTRUMENT OF THE STUDY

A pre-test and post-test in the class 4th & 5th were developed to evaluate the Academic Achievement of students before and after the completion of the experiment. The researcher made a plan based on Universal Design for Learning and executed in the class and pre-test was developed in the light of test construction technique. Post test was based on Multiple Choice Item.

Pre-test

Pre-test (appendix) for class 4th and 5th were administered before the treatment. The aim of pre-test was to assess the status of knowledge of students before the experiment. There were 25 multiple choice items in the pre-test. Test was checked by giving one mark to right answer and no mark was given to wrong answer. There was no negative marking. The total score was 25.

Post-test

After the four weeks treatment (chapters were taught through Universal Design of Learning) a post-test was administered. Result of post-test was recorded. The chapters selected from the 4th and 5th class. The purpose of post-test was to find out the difference in the Academic Achievement of the students after the treatment. There were 25 Multiple Choice Items in the post test. Test was scored by giving one mark to right answer and no marks were given to wrong answers. There was no negative marking. The total score was 25.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In the present research, the researcher deals with analysis interpretation of data regarding student’s Academic Achievement after the use of Universal Design of Learning in Inclusive Classroom. To find out the effectiveness of Universal Design of Learning at elementary level, first of all obtained scores of individual students were prepared and presented in tables. In Second step the frequency distribution of raw scores was prepared and presented in tabular form. Third step was the calculation of mean and standard deviation on the pre and post scores. In the Final step, t test was applied to find out the difference in student’s Academic Achievement after the use of Universal Design of Learning.

Table 1- Mean and Standard Deviation of the Raw Score

	N	Mean	SD
Pre-Test	40	15.15	2.38
Post- Test	40	17.32	3.96

Table 2- Frequency Distribution of Pre-Test Score

F	Score
5-7	3
8-10	2
11-13	8
14-16	16
17-19	4
20-22	2
23-25	5

N=40

The data presented in the table provides information about pre-test and it showed that majority of students were average in respect to their academic achievement.

Table3-Frequency Distribution of Post-Test Score

F	Score
5-7	2
8-10	4
11-13	5
14-16	6
17-19	4
20-22	11
23-25	8

N=40

The table above presents the frequency distribution of post-test scores. It provides information about students' performance after the treatment. The data indicate that students' academic achievement improved significantly following the treatment, which is also clearly illustrated in the table below.

Table 4 Significance of difference between pre-test and post-test academic achievement scores of students.

	N	Mean	SD	t	p
Pre-Test	40	15.15	2.38	2.97	.00
Post- Test	40	17.32	3.96		

Df-78, SEM-.731

The above tables shows that the actual difference between the mean of pre-test and post-test score was found to be highly significant because the calculated t value is higher than critical t value at .05 level of significance and is also significant at 0.00 level. The null hypothesis is, therefore, rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significance difference between the mean academic achievement scores of pre-test and post-test after the use of universal design of learning in Inclusive Classroom.

FINDINGS

On the basis of the statistical analysis of the data, the following findings are made:
The mean score of pre-test was 15.15 with 2.38 standard deviation while the mean score of post-test was 17.32 with 3.96 standard deviation.
Difference between the academic achievement score of pre-test and post-test was highly significant because the calculated t value is higher than the critical t value at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

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